

State Versus Dynamic Variables, Special Relativity and Quantum Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Dec. 27, 2024

In previous notes, we argued that free particle quantum mechanics seems to be linked to the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ in that A is degenerate for $t = t_0 + n\hbar/E$ and $x = x_0 + n\hbar/p$, where n is an integer.

Here, we wish to investigate this idea in more detail based on two considerations. The first is the notion of state variables versus dynamic and the second is the more general notion of a universal state invariant, based on $-Et + px$, which applies to intervals $-E dt + p dx$ and not only to frames linked by different constant velocities $-v$, but also to different m_0 (rest mass) values as well. In other words, every rest mass and constant v is linked in that it has the same $A=0 = -E dt + p dx$, where $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$.

This is motivated by the observation that for $p=0$ (in the rest frame) $m_0 v = m_0' v' = 0$ because $v=0$. In other words, $p=0$ links different m_0 values (or erases their information) suggesting that one might also want to erase m_0 information from $-E dt$. In other words, there is not only a link between m_0 at rest and different $-v$ frames, but also between different m_0 values. This is based on the notion of dt and dx behaving as state variables instead of the usual Newtonian and even special relativistic view of x', t' as dynamic (trajectory based variables). We define a state variable as one which describes the kind (magnitude or type) of interaction which occurs, not one which describes when, where or whether it will occur. This latter set we call dynamic variables. As a result, if dx is a state variable, it must describe how an interaction occurs, which is what happens in a 2-slit experiment.

State Versus Dynamic Variables

We define state variables as one which describes the type of interaction which occurs (e.g. magnitudes). For example, rest mass m_0 is a state variable because it represents inertia (which appears if one pushes on an object). Kinetic energy and momentum are also state variables. Time and position, on the other hand, are dynamic variables. They determine when and where an interaction may occur, but not the magnitude or type of interaction. In Newtonian mechanics, both dynamic and state variables appear. This is also the case in special relativity. In equilibrium classical thermodynamics, state variables appear and one ignores the dynamical variables of the individual molecules.

A main focus of this note is to inquire whether dt , dx (time and spatial intervals) may be state variables. Certainly, x and t which appear in both Newtonian mechanics and special relativity are trajectory based dynamical variables and not state ones. On the other hand, \hbar/E and \hbar/p from quantum mechanics are state variables, according to our definition, because they describe the kind of interaction which may occur. In particular, \hbar/p suggests that a particle with constant p may interact with both slits of a two-slit apparatus if the width/spacing of the slits are of the order of \hbar/p . This means that dx describes the kind of interaction which may occur. Dx and dt from quantum mechanics do not appear directly in Newtonian mechanics and special relativity, yet seem to be present in nature and so we ask: Why?

Lorentz Invariants

We argue that special relativity gives a clue to why there may be state variables linked with dx and dt intervals because it considers an equivalence between a particle at rest and its versions as seen by different frames moving with different constant $-v$ values. We argue that the equivalence of different frames seems to represent a kind of equivalence of an overall state, but this must be defined explicitly.

We start with the fact that special relativity uses both state and dynamical variables. The rest mass m_0 , E and p are state variables. E and p depend explicitly on m_0 and v (velocity). X and t , on the other hand, are dynamical variables, they are linked to a trajectory. Thus, Lorentz invariants are a mixed bag.

$$-EE + pcpc = -m_0c^2 m_0c^2 \quad ((1a))$$

represents a state equation, or rather a linking equation between two states (p,E) and $(p=0, m_0c^2)$ which are equivalent.

$$-ctct + xx = -ct'ct' + x'x' \quad ((1b))$$

represents dynamical variables. These are associated with a trajectory $x'=vt'+B$, not with the strength or type of interaction which occurs, but rather with if, when and where.

Finally,

$$-Et+px = A \quad ((1c))$$

represents a hybrid, combining state variables (p,E) with dynamic ones (x,ct) . We note that A is an invariant at the level of each trajectory point (x,t) across $-v$ frames. In other words, A is the same across different frames for only one (x,t) point in each. It is not a global invariant indicating that each frame is really an equivalent state (even though it has different p,E state variables). At this point, there is no reason to associate t and x (or even intervals) with any notion other than that of dynamical variables.

P=0 in the Rest Frame

We argue that $p=0$ in the rest frame may suggest that a more universal invariant is present. $p=0$ means that for $m_{01} \neq m_{02}$, one still has $p=0$. In other words, in the rest frame, p does not distinguish between different rest masses (with respect to momentum). Boosting to other $-v$ frames means that m_{01} and m_{02} are not equivalent in these boosted frames, but their $p=0$ is in the rest frame. Thus, we suggest that there is a more global invariance present. Somehow one must construct an invariant which treats m_{01} and m_{02} states on the same footing. This is not the $A = -Et+px$ framework which uses x,t as trajectory points. Even intervals would be based on trajectories.

Instead, we argue that if one goes into the rest frame, then one has $p=0$ for both m_{01} and m_{02} . On the other hand, $m_{01}c^2$ and $m_{02}c^2$ (i.e. energies, not momentum) are distinct,

suggesting that one has overall different states. Certainly, m_1 and m_2 are different and are state variables, but mathematically one may consider m_1 cc dt with $dt=1/m_1$ cc as representing a product of two state variables such that there is no m_1 information present any longer. $p=0$ already ensures that m_1 and m_2 are erased, but to be put on equal footing with m_1 cc dt, one may consider:

$P dx$ with $p \rightarrow 0$ such that $dx \rightarrow$ infinite with $pdx=1$ ((2))

Then $-Edt + pdx = 0$, not only for all $-v$ states for the same m_1 , if $dx=h\bar{c}/p$ and $dt=h\bar{c}/E$, but also for different rest mass values. In other words, $-E dt + p dx=0$ is not simply the Lorentzinvariant, but rather defines an equivalence of all m_0 rest masses and their forms seen from frames moving with all $-v$ values, if one introduces state variables $dx=h\bar{c}/p$ and $dt=h\bar{c}/E$. We argue that $p=0$ which erases rest mass information suggests this approach.

As a result, $dx=h\bar{c}/p$ and $dt=h\bar{c}/E$ must represent state variables because they have nothing to do with trajectories (dynamical variables). According to the definition above, they must describe a kind of interaction, not when and where it occurs. In other words, $dx=h\bar{c}/p$ suggests an x interval based on the state variable p which must describe interaction within this interval. If one has a two-slit apparatus separated by about $h\bar{c}/p$, we suggest that this means there are interactions with both slits due to the interaction interval $dx=h\bar{c}/p$.

Different state variables p, E may combine with a second set of state variables $h\bar{c}/p$ and $h\bar{c}/E$ to create an $A=0$ invariant $= -E dt + p dx$ which applies to all constant p states. We argue that there seems to be something universal about constant p states, not only those with the same rest mass as in special relativity. The clue to this universality of constant p seems to be contained in $p=0$ in the rest frame which does not distinguish between m_1 and m_2 .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that there exist both state and dynamical variables. We suggest that the former describe the kind of interaction (magnitude etc) which occurs, while the latter, when and where. Newtonian mechanics and special relativity include both kinds of variables. For example, m_0, E, p are state variables, while x and t are dynamical ones. x and t are not linked at all with state variables, i.e. do not describe how an interaction may occur. Quantum mechanics, however, differs with this viewpoint because $dx=h\bar{c}/p$ shows that a particle with constant p may interact over the range dx and not simply at the center-of-mass point. This is manifested in the two-slit experiment in which an entangled state is created when a particle interacts with both slits, we argue. Thus, we try to investigate how one may find dx and dt intervals which are state variables.

We argue that the clue lies in the rest frame of special relativity. For $p=0$, m_1 and m_2 , different state variables, have the same momentum. Thus, they are not distinguished. We suggest that this is the basis for creating a universal state which holds for all m_0 and constant p values, not just a given m_0 linked to different $-v$ frames and $A = -Et+px$. In other words, t and x in $-Et+px$ from special relativity pertain to a specific trajectory point such that A is the same for

this specific point in all -v frames. A different trajectory point implies a different A value and different m_0 points, a completely different system in special relativity.

We suggest that $p=0$ does not consider m_{01} and m_{02} as belonging to different systems, but erases their unique information. If one considers $p dx = p \hbar/p$, then as $p \rightarrow 0$, $\hbar/p \rightarrow \infty$ such that $p dx > 1$. This suggests that one introduce $dt = \hbar/m_0 c$, which allows $-E dt$ to erase rest mass information. The combination $-E dt + p dx = 0$ then holds not only for the same rest mass in different -v frames, but also for different m_0 values. We note that even though E and p are state variables, they have different physical properties. For example, p is proportional to impulse, but different m_0 values may have the same p and different E. They then impart the same impulse, but have different energy which manifests itself differently in other interactions. E and p are, as a result, separated in $-E dt + p dx$ for physical reasons. Overall, by introducing the two new state variables dt and dx, one may create a global invariant which applies to all m_0 and all constant p values. This means, however, that dt and dx must describe a kind of interaction because they are state variables and not dynamical ones. $dx = \hbar/p$ defines an interval, presumably of interaction, which is manifested in a 2-slit experiment if slit widths are about \hbar/p apart.